

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the importance of pedagogical technologies in the educational process. Pedagogical technologies are an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of education in the modern education system, individualizing students' learning, and improving the quality of the teaching process through interactive methods. The article discusses innovative pedagogical technologies, their main types, and their integration into the educational process. It also highlights the role of pedagogical technologies in developing the teacher's professional skills, forming independent thinking and creative thinking of students. The results of the study are aimed at revealing the effectiveness of using modern technologies in the educational process.

Keywords: Modern method, method, students, activity, interactive method, lesson, technology.

Today, deep reforms are being carried out in various areas of life in new Uzbekistan. This is especially evident in the education system. Legal normative documents on the development of education are a vivid example of this. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Addresses of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis "State Program for Youth", the new edition of the Law "On Education", the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 29, 2020 No. PF-6097 "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of Science and Technology until 2030" have become of great importance in the development of education and science in our country. Based on the new edition of the Law "On Education", the main principles, education system, types and forms of education in the field of education have been clearly defined. At a new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the issues of reforming the education system, creating a high-quality education structure, and transforming continuous education into a new effective process are becoming increasingly relevant. The effective use of pedagogical technologies in the development of education is an important factor in the effective conduct of teaching processes. Pedagogical technologies, which are an important

component of the modern educational process, include various teaching methods, techniques and approaches that help teachers and students achieve the desired result and educational goals.

According to the Russian scientist B.T. Likhachev, pedagogical technology is a set of psychological and pedagogical views that determine the purpose, content and methods of education, and is an organizational and methodological tool of the teaching and upbringing process.

The effective use of modern pedagogical educational technologies and their proper organization ensure effective and interactive education. The correct selection of technologies in educational institutions and the teacher's competence in using these technologies increase the level of student learning through his professional approach.

The following factors are very important in the use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process:

- 1. Integration of educational technologies;**
- 2. Training and support of teachers;**
- 3. Adaptation of curricula;**
- 4. Monitoring and evaluation of the educational process;**
- 5. Results-based improvement.**

When integrating educational technologies, it is necessary to pay attention to the selection of technologies and testing of technologies. In this case, based on the age and interests of the student, modern techniques can be used, video demonstrations, the most important thing is to be able to choose them correctly and test them in practice.

By training and supporting teachers, it is possible to ensure that their professional development always takes the right approach. Modern technologies make the teaching process more interactive and effective. Adaptation of curricula is important. In this case, the teacher can use new and unusual approaches to lesson planning, use interactive methods, including games, problem-solving, and group work. Each teacher should monitor and report on the learning process and assess student understanding. In this case, the impact of technology on the quality of education is regularly monitored. Technology can be used to more accurately measure the level of student knowledge. For example, electronic tests and self-assessment tools play an important role in identifying student interests and activities, as well as their internal capabilities. Analyzing the impact of technology used in the lesson is one of the important tasks. Based on the results, it is possible to adjust

technologies and teaching methods through feedback from teachers and students. In conclusion, it can be said that modern pedagogical technologies serve to improve the educational process, deepen students' knowledge, and develop their independent thinking skills. These technologies help to increase the interactivity of the teaching process, strengthen the personal approach and develop the professional competence of teachers. Therefore, the widespread introduction and development of modern pedagogical technologies remains one of the urgent issues of the education system.

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